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Research Intensity in the Italian Regions

It grew by 47% on average between 2004 and 2020

Istat calculates the value of research intensity. Research intensity is defined as the percentage of expenditure on intramural research and development activities carried out by companies, public institutions, universities (public and private) and the non-profit sector as a percentage of GDP. Spending and GDP are considered in millions of current euros. The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2020 for the 20 Italian regions.

Research intensity in the Italian regions in 2020. The analysis of data on the intensity of research in the different Italian regions offers an in-depth look at the distribution and commitment of individual areas in the scientific and technological field. This uneven picture reflects the complexity of the Italian landscape, characterized by various socioeconomic and structural dynamics. First of all, a polarization between the northern and southern regions clearly emerges, with Piedmont and Emilia-Romagna leading the way as centers of excellence in research. This trend could be attributed to a combination of factors, including the presence of prestigious academic institutions, advanced research centers and a stronger industrial infrastructure. Lombardy, despite its leadership position in the national economy, shows a moderate level of research intensity. This suggests that the correlation between economic development and research commitment is not always linear, and other elements, such as the diversification of the industrial sector or the focus on specific research fields, can influence the outcome. Southern Italy, represented by regions such as Calabria and Basilicata, faces more obvious challenges in terms of research intensity. The reasons for this disparity may be multiple, including limited infrastructure, less rewarding job opportunities and a need for greater investment in education and research. Central regions, such as Lazio and Umbria, are placed in the middle of the ranking, indicating significant involvement in scientific research. These regions could benefit from a combination of factors, including the presence of centers of excellence and effective governance in promoting innovation. Reading the data invites reflection on the opportunities and challenges that emerge from this heterogeneous scenario. Targeted development policies, investments in education and research, and incentives for collaboration between the public and private sectors could help reduce regional disparities and promote a more balanced and research-friendly environment across the country. In conclusion, the analysis of data on research intensity in Italy paves the way for a broader dialogue on the need for development strategies and targeted policies, which take into account regional specificities and contribute to consolidating Italy as a dynamic hub and innovative in the European and global context.

Change in research intensity between 2004 and 2020 in the Italian regions. The analysis of data on research intensity in the various Italian regions in the period 2004-2020 provides an eloquent overview of the evolutionary dynamics in the scientific and technological field. Numerous considerations emerge from these figures, highlighting significant trends and substantial variations across regions. Molise stands out as a case of notable growth, recording a 166.67% increase in search intensity. Despite starting from relatively low initial levels, this increase indicates a tangible effort and growing commitment to promoting scientific research activities in the region. Veneto and Marche

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are also experiencing strong growth, with percentage variations of 115.63% and 94.34% respectively. These data suggest a clear willingness of these regions to invest in research and development activities over the years, indicating a sustained growth dynamic. Emilia-Romagna emerges as one of the most dynamic regions, with a significant increase in research intensity of 88.39%. This could be the result of targeted investments in research infrastructure and a continued commitment to scientific innovation. The performance of the northern regions presents notable differences. While Piedmont recorded an increase of 42.94%, Lombardy showed a more moderate growth of 28.3%. These disparities can be influenced by factors such as economic and industrial structure, the presence of academic institutions and research investment strategies. Some regions, such as Lazio, Campania and Sicily, show moderate or slightly positive percentage changes. This could indicate that, despite the presence of research centers or academic institutions, growth could be limited by other factors or the need for more targeted development strategies. Basilicata records a moderate growth of 28.3%, indicating a constant commitment to promoting scientific research. However, it is important to underline that the regions of Southern Italy continue to face significant challenges in closing the gap with the northern regions. In summary, the analysis of variations in research intensity underlines the complexity of the Italian panorama, highlighting regions that have made substantial progress and others that may require more incisive development strategies. Equity in access to research opportunities on a national scale may require a coordinated and targeted approach to promote sustainable growth and innovation across the country.

Research intensity in the Italian macro-regions. The analysis of the evolution of research intensity in the various Italian macro-areas in the period between 2004 and 2020 provides a significant picture of regional dynamics in the scientific and technological field. These data reveal trends that go beyond simple numerical increase, offering food for thought on the development of research activities in different geographical contexts. The North emerges as the main focus of research in Italy, showing an increase from 1.07 to 1.63, with a percentage change of 52.34%. This region, comprising the Northwest and Northeast, has consistently maintained leadership in promoting innovation and scientific development. Within the North, the Northeast stands out for its remarkable growth of 90.91%, underlining considerable commitment to promoting scientific research. In parallel, the North-West, although showing a more moderate growth of 32.50%, contributes significantly to the national research panorama. The Centre's macro-area, with an increase of 35.43%, demonstrates a growing commitment to research activities. This data suggests that the central region is progressively consolidating its presence in the Italian scientific panorama, albeit with a lower growth rate than the North. The South and the Islands show more moderate growth, with percentage variations of 25.00% and 12.50% respectively. These data indicate an awareness of the importance of scientific research in these regions, but highlight the need for targeted efforts to close the gap with the northern regions. The convergence between the North and the South, although significant, highlights the persistence of regional inequalities. This phenomenon underlines the importance of regional development policies that aim to create a favorable environment for scientific research throughout the national territory. In conclusion, the analysis of Italian macro-areas in the context of scientific research reflects a complex and articulated reality. As the North continues to lead in innovation, it is encouraging to note the efforts of other regions to actively promote research. The need for targeted regional development strategies, equitable investments and collaborations between the public and private sectors emerges as a key element to ensure a more balanced and sustainable scientific research landscape in Italy.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering with k-Means algorithm is presented below. Three clusters are identified:

- Cluster 0: Liguria, Lombardy, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Tuscany, Campania;

- Cluster 1: Valle d'Aosta, Umbria, Marche, Abruzzo, Molise, Puglia, Sicily, Sardinia;
- Cluster 2: Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Lazio.

We note that considering the value of these clusters it is possible to create the following ordering i.e. $C2 > C0 > C1$. It follows that the regions of the Centre-North tend to have much higher levels of research intensity than the southern regions with the sole exception of Campania. In fact, Campania has higher levels of research intensity than other southern regions and shares the cluster with relevant regions with high per capita income such as Lombardy and Veneto.

Econometric model for estimating the value of research intensity. Below I present a model for estimating the intensity of research in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2020 in light of the ISTAT-BES indicators relating to the innovation and research system. The data were analyzed using various econometric models, namely Panel Data with Fixed Effects, Panel Data with Variable Effects, Pooled Ordinary Least Squares, and Weighted Least Squares-WLS. The following equation was estimated:

$$RI_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(PTP)_{it} + \beta_2(IPS)_{it} + \beta_3(RIU)_{it} + \beta_5(IFC)_{it}$$

Where $i=20$ and $t=[2004;2020]$.

There is a positive relationship between IR-research intensity and:

- Propensity towards patenting-PTP: the relationship between research intensity and patenting activity is closely interconnected, characterized by a positive relationship that manifests itself through different aspects. When an organization dedicates significant resources to research and development, it often leads to new discoveries and innovations. These advances, resulting from sustained research efforts, often become the subject of patents to protect associated intellectual property rights. A key element of this relationship is market competitiveness. Companies, eager to maintain or gain a competitive advantage, use patenting as a strategic tool. By protecting innovations through patents, they make it more difficult for competitors to copy or imitate such advances, thus solidifying their position in the market. Access to finance is another crucial aspect. Organizations engaged in intensive research often rely on external funding, such as venture capital investments or government grants. In this context, patents can act as collateral, demonstrating a tangible commitment to innovation and providing a legal basis for protecting new technologies. Building a patent portfolio is a common practice among research-oriented companies. Accumulating patents means building a solid base of legally protected knowledge, which can be exploited in different directions. Such a wallet not only protects, but can also be used as leverage to negotiate deals, collaborations or partnerships. Collaboration is a further element facilitated by patenting. Companies involved in intensive research can establish partnerships more easily by basing the collaboration on well-defined intellectual property rights. Patents, in this context, act as a glue for more stable agreements and mutual benefits. Finally, the possibility of monetizing patents is an additional incentive for companies. Beyond mere protection, patents offer the prospect of generating revenue through selling, licensing, or commercializing the covered technologies. This element of economic value helps to further justify investments in research and development. In summary, the positive relationship between research intensity and patenting reflects the tendency of organizations to actively protect and exploit the results of their research activities through the patent system.
- Innovation of the production system-IPS: the intensity of research and the innovation of the production system are two elements which, when interconnected, create a virtuous

combination for the development and growth of businesses. Intensive research constitutes the fundamental basis from which new knowledge and discoveries arise, forming the fertile ground for innovation in the production system. When organizations invest significantly in research and development, this not only generates new ideas, but fuels the process of creating new technologies. The introduction of these technologies into the production system becomes the engine that drives substantial improvements, from the optimization of production processes to the implementation of advanced methodologies. The main objective is often the optimization of the production processes themselves. The adoption of new technologies and workflow innovation help make the entire system more efficient and effective. Furthermore, optimization can result in a reduction in operating costs and an increase in market competitiveness. The ability to adapt to changing market needs is another crucial aspect. Continuous research allows companies to anticipate trends, understand new consumer demands and quickly adapt the production system accordingly. In an increasingly dynamic economic environment, this flexibility is essential to maintain relevance and competitiveness in the marketplace. The connection between research and innovation in the production system is also evident in differentiation on the market. Companies that invest in research and development are able to offer unique products or services, distinguishing themselves from competitors. This differentiation creates a sustainable competitive advantage and helps build a reputation for innovation in the industry. Furthermore, the attraction of talent and qualified resources is often a direct consequence of a serious commitment to research. Brilliant minds attracted to an environment that promotes innovation become the driving force for translating research ideas into concrete solutions and tangible improvements in the production system. In conclusion, the positive relationship between research intensity and innovation in the production system is evident in the way in which research creates the basis for innovations which, in turn, shape and improve the way in which companies produce and compete on the market. This virtuous cycle not only stimulates business growth, but also helps develop and maintain a prosperous and dynamic economy.

- Availability of at least one computer and an Internet connection in the family - IFC: The connection between the intensity of research and the availability of at least one computer and an Internet connection in the family is a profound link that manifests itself in multiple ways, outlining the fundamental role of technology in facilitating and enhancing research activities. First, the presence of a computer and an Internet connection provides individuals with unprecedented access to a vast treasure trove of resources and information. Through the network, it is possible to access virtual libraries, scientific databases and specialized publications, opening the doors to a world of knowledge that goes beyond the physical boundaries of traditional libraries. Active participation in research is further encouraged by the availability of such technological resources. The ability to conduct online research, participate in virtual communities of experts and contribute to collaborative research projects becomes possible thanks to an Internet connection. This not only democratizes access to research opportunities, but also stimulates broader and more inclusive participation by individuals from diverse geographic and demographic backgrounds. Scientific communication is greatly facilitated by a robust technological infrastructure. The Internet connection allows the immediate sharing of results, ideas and projects between researchers located all over the world. Online forums, collaborative platforms and academic social networks serve as virtual bridges connecting brilliant minds, accelerating the flow of information and improving collaboration. Furthermore, the availability of a computer in the family allows the installation of specialized analysis tools and software essential for advanced research. Modeling software, simulation applications and statistical packages become

accessible, providing the tools needed to tackle complex challenges across different research disciplines. Technology not only facilitates research activity, but also supports continuous learning. Online courses, webinars and digital educational resources become accessible to anyone, promoting the constant updating of skills and allowing researchers to stay abreast of new discoveries and methodologies. Finally, the presence of technological resources in the family helps to reduce disparities in access to research opportunities. Democratizing access to technology can play a significant role in including individuals from different sections of society into the research community, promoting diversification and innovation. In conclusion, the positive relationship between research intensity and the availability of computers and Internet connection in the family reflects the crucial importance of technology in facilitating access, participation and collaboration in scientific and academic research. This link is essential to foster an inclusive, dynamic and future-oriented research environment.

There is a negative relationship between IR-research intensity and:

- **Regular Internet Users-RIU:** The negative relationship between search intensity and regular Internet users may represent an interesting point of reflection in an era where digital connectivity is pervasive. While the Internet offers unprecedented access to a vast array of information, resources, and research tools, some contexts may suggest a contrasting dynamic. A possible scenario could emerge if regular Internet users mainly engage in online entertainment activities or superficial social interactions. In this context, the wide variety of digital content could act as a distraction, taking away time and energy that could otherwise be invested in more in-depth and concentrated research activities. Research, which requires significant mental effort and the ability to immerse yourself in complex topics, may be hindered by excessive use of the Internet for recreational or social purposes. Ease of access to rapid and fragmented information could lead to a superficial understanding of topics, contributing to a tendency towards seeking immediate gratification rather than deepening knowledge. Furthermore, dependence on social media could negatively influence the propensity for in-depth research. Constant interaction on social platforms could create an environment in which the sharing of short and immediate content prevails over dedication to more in-depth studies. The overabundance of information online could be another key driver. The breadth of content available on the Internet could lead to information overload, making it difficult for regular users to discern between reliable and unreliable sources, and discouraging them from delving deeper into certain topics. It should be emphasized that the hypothesized negative relationship is not intrinsic to the Internet, but rather is influenced by how individuals choose to use the technology. The conscious and targeted approach to the use of the Internet can support research by facilitating access to resources, scientific publications and advanced tools. In conclusion, the negative relationship between search intensity and regular Internet users could be influenced by various behavioral and usage factors. The balance between conscious use of the Internet and engagement in deep research is a critical aspect that deserves attention in an era where digital technology can act as both a catalyst and a barrier to deep research and learning advanced.

Conclusions. The intensity of research has grown in all Italian regions and macro-regions. However, a significant gap persists between the South and the Centre-North in terms of research intensity. Improving the intensity of research in the Italian regions is a challenge that requires joint commitment and a long-term strategic vision. In this context, several factors need to be taken into consideration to stimulate a more dynamic and prosperous research environment. First, it is essential to increase investment in research and development, both by the public and private sectors. Allocating financial

resources to innovative research projects and creating tax incentives for companies investing in R&D can help stimulate growth in the sector. In parallel, the development of advanced research infrastructures is crucial. The creation of centers of excellence, specialized laboratories and technological hubs can attract talent and encourage collaboration between academic institutes, industries and research bodies. The promotion of collaborations between universities, industry and institutions is fundamental to guarantee the transferability of knowledge and the practical application of research results. Incentivizing the formation of strategic partnerships can help create a more cohesive innovation ecosystem. Another aspect to consider is support for training and skills development. Investing in the training of qualified personnel through doctoral programs, masters and specialized courses is essential to guarantee the presence of a highly qualified workforce. Creating an environment conducive to startups and spin-offs is also crucial. Encouraging the birth of new high-tech businesses through tax breaks and subsidized financing can encourage the growth of innovative sectors. The international mobility of researchers and students is a key element in enriching the research landscape. Promoting international exchanges and collaborations can lead to a greater diversity of perspectives and contribute to the creation of more robust research networks. Finally, it is essential to actively involve the local community in research activities and raise awareness of the importance of science and innovation. Civil society participation can help create a sense of ownership and ensure long-term support for research activities. In summary, improving research intensity in Italian regions requires a combination of targeted investments, strategic collaborations, skills development and active community involvement. Only through an integrated and sustainable approach can we build a vibrant research ecosystem capable of generating significant impacts on society and the economy.

Declarations

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Appendix

Variable and Acronyms

A97	Research intensity	RI
A98	Propensity towards patenting	PTP
A99	Innovation of the production system	IPS
A103	Regular internet users	RIU
A104	Availability of at least one computer and Internet connection in the family	ICF

Intensità di Ricerca nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020

Model 52: Random-effects (GLS), using 375 observations
Using Nerlove's transformation
Included 20 cross-sectional units
Time-series length: minimum 17, maximum 19
Dependent variable: A97

	coefficient	std. error	z	p-value
const	0.263364	0.0921914	2.857	0.0043 ***
A98	0.00503481	0.000495814	10.15	3.16e-024 ***
A99	0.00528570	0.000679596	7.778	7.39e-015 ***
A103	-0.0180609	0.00343485	-5.258	1.46e-07 ***
A104	0.0227055	0.00380897	5.961	2.51e-09 ***

Mean dependent var 0.947013 S.D. dependent var 0.521467
Sum squared resid 58.67759 S.E. of regression 0.397694
Log-likelihood -184.3142 Akaike criterion 378.6283
Schwarz criterion 398.2630 Hannan-Quinn 386.4234
rho 0.232618 Durbin-Watson 1.420486

'Between' variance = 0.0738593
'Within' variance = 0.0855468
mean theta = 0.758703
corr(y,yhat)^2 = 0.423629

Joint test on named regressors -
Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(4) = 262.967
with p-value = 1.04601e-55

Breusch-Pagan test -
Null hypothesis: Variance of the unit-specific error = 0
Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(1) = 602.947
with p-value = 3.82698e-133

Hausman test -
Null hypothesis: GLS estimates are consistent
Asymptotic test statistic: Chi-square(4) = 2.75938
with p-value = 0.598864

Model 50: Fixed-effects, using 375 observations
Included 20 cross-sectional units
Time-series length: minimum 17, maximum 19
Dependent variable: A97

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.259699	0.0695858	3.732	0.0002 ***
A98	0.00507294	0.000533088	9.516	2.98e-019 ***
A99	0.00528256	0.000681795	7.748	1.01e-013 ***
A103	-0.0180964	0.00349271	-5.181	3.73e-07 ***
A104	0.0227912	0.00385566	5.911	8.05e-09 ***

Mean dependent var 0.947013 S.D. dependent var 0.521467
Sum squared resid 32.08006 S.E. of regression 0.302318
LSDV R-squared 0.684565 Within R-squared 0.414361
LSDV F(23, 351) 33.11954 F-value(F) 9.51e-74
Log-likelihood -71.09733 Akaike criterion 190.1947
Schwarz criterion 284.4409 Hannan-Quinn 227.6109
rho 0.232618 Durbin-Watson 1.420486

Joint test on named regressors -
Test statistic: F(4, 351) = 62.0863
with p-value = P(F(4, 351) > 62.0863) = 1.22087e-39

Test for differing group intercepts -
Null hypothesis: The groups have a common intercept
Test statistic: F(19, 351) = 15.263
with p-value = P(F(19, 351) > 15.263) = 1.96859e-35

Clusterizzazione delle Regioni Italiane per Intensità di Ricerca nel 2020

Model 49: Pooled OLS, using 375 observations
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Time-series length: minimum 17, maximum 19
 Dependent variable: A97

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.305539	0.0774627	3.944	9.57e-05 ***
A98	0.00485632	0.000377197	12.87	1.34e-031 ***
A99	0.00535018	0.000894813	5.979	5.29e-09 ***
A103	-0.0165288	0.00410911	-4.022	6.98e-05 ***
A104	0.0206465	0.00463380	4.456	1.11e-05 ***

Mean dependent var	0.947013	S.D. dependent var	0.521467
Sum squared resid	58.58465	S.E. of regression	0.397916
R-squared	0.423952	Adjusted R-squared	0.417725
F(4, 370)	68.07701	P-value(F)	3.84e-43
Log-likelihood	-184.0169	Akaike criterion	378.0339
Schwarz criterion	397.6685	Hannan-Quinn	385.8290
rho	0.603606	Durbin-Watson	0.767503

Model 51: WLS, using 375 observations
 Included 20 cross-sectional units
 Dependent variable: A97
 Weights based on per-unit error variances

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.330318	0.0561368	5.884	8.97e-09 ***
A98	0.00476316	0.000322204	14.78	3.47e-039 ***
A99	0.00459878	0.000480769	6.755	5.55e-011 ***
A103	-0.0169331	0.00286338	-5.914	7.61e-09 ***
A104	0.0197214	0.00327212	6.027	4.04e-09 ***

Statistics based on the weighted data:

Sum squared resid	357.4748	S.E. of regression	0.992928
R-squared	0.503289	Adjusted R-squared	0.497919
F(4, 370)	93.72507	P-value(F)	5.66e-55
Log-likelihood	-523.1280	Akaike criterion	1056.256
Schwarz criterion	1075.891	Hannan-Quinn	1064.051

Statistics based on the original data:

Mean dependent var	0.947013	S.D. dependent var	0.521467
Sum squared resid	60.34654	S.E. of regression	0.403855